

Update on the ILRS

Michael Pearlman
Claudia Carabajal
Erricos Pavlis
ILRS Central Bureau

GGOS Days 2022
Munich, Germany
November 14th – 15th, 2022

Current and Planned ILRS Network

- New operational station in Tenerife and engineering station in Stuttgart
- Russian testing of new Toshka SLR systems in co-location at Mendeleevo and Irkutsk
- New stations scheduled for operation in 2023: Yebes (Spain), La Plata (Argentina), Metsahovi (Finland), Mt. Abu and Ponmundi (India), and Tsukuba (Japan); and in 2025: Matera (Italy)
- NASA/NASA affiliated: Ny Ålesund (NMA, Norway) (2025), McDonald (2026), GGAO (2027), and Haleakala (2028)
- New Russia stations planned at Ensenada (Mexico), Java (Indonesia), Canary Islands (Spain) (no recent update)

The ESA Laser Ranging Station at Tenerife, Spain

Station deployed in June 2021

- R-C Telescope (80 cm)
- Visible and IR SPADs
- **Nd:YAG (7ps, 500μJ @1064 nm)**
- Laser safety system
- Remote Operations

Satellite Laser Ranging

- **SLR Operation at 532 nm and 1064 nm** since end of 2021. **Range biases < 10mm confirmed at both wavelengths**
- More than 850 passes uploaded to EDC mainly at 1064 nm
- ILRS engineering station; Validation completed in April 2022
- On-demand SLR support

Space debris observations in 2023 tikeframe

- FLI ML16070 camera for passive observations
- **Station upgrades by 2023 for SDLR, targeted range accuracy 10's cm**
- SDLR networked operations in cooperation with other debris tracking stations

Optical communications (CCSDS O3K)

- **Detection and decoding of optical downlink signals from LEO missions**
- Laser beacon uplink for satellite acquisition (6W @1590 nm)

IGN/CNIG Laser Ranging Station in Yebees, Spain

YLARA – Yebees Laser Ranging Station

Preliminar Station Design (Estudio AIA, 2021)

➤ To be operational on March 31st, 2023

Telescope and Mount

- Biaxial telescope. Az/El mount, several foci
 - Receiving system: $D_{\text{Main mirror}} = 70 \text{ cm}$
 - Transmitting system (Coudé focus): $D_{\text{Mirrors}} = 45,7 \text{ mm}$
 - Beam pointing accuracy: $\leq 3''$
 - High slew rate: $12^\circ/\text{s}$ Az and El

Dome

- Slit dome, 5.3 m diameter

Laser subsystem (piggyback configuration)

- Solid state pulsed laser
 - Repetition rate: 1000 Hz (adjustable)
 - Wavelengths: 532 nm and 1064 nm (Nd:YAG)
 - Energy: 0,26 mJ @ 532 nm, 0,35 mJ @ 1064 nm
 - Pulse width: 7 ps @ 532 nm, 8,5 ps @ 1064 nm
 - Transmitting system: $D_{\text{Mirrors}} = 75 \text{ mm}$

Detector Package

- CSPAD + IR Detector

Operational: early 2023

Baader Dome and Officina Stellare Telescope Assembly

The miniSLR[®] - Design

- High-performance:
 - ◆ Sub-cm precision for Normal Points
 - ◆ Range from LEO up to GNSS targets
 - ◆ Long-term stability
 - ◆ Remote-controlled and highly automated
- Low budget:
 - ◆ Small footprint
 - ◆ Transportable (can be integrated at factory)
 - ◆ Simple design
 - ◆ Fully encapsulated (no dome)
 - ◆ Based on amateur mount and small telescope

*The miniSLR at German Aerospace Centre
(in operation since February 2022)*

- ILRS/ Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) Tracking Campaign on the IRNSS synchronous satellite constellation (7 satellites) planned for 2023;
- Seeks uniform coverage over the IRNSS satellites from the ILRS network plus new Indian stations in Ponmudi (southern India) and Mt Abu (northern India)
- 10-day sessions would be organized into two satellites at a time
- Map of satellite orbits and desirable dispersion of Normal Points in orbit

Map showing orbits of 1I and 1B satellites

Desirable dispersion of Normal Points

- First test with the ILRS network conducted April 17 – 30, 2022 gave significant data from Yarragadee and Grasse; some data from several others
- Further campaigns await evidence that progress is being made on the new SLR systems

Compact distribution of small retroreflectors reduces the variation of return signal strength as a function of aspect angle

Estimated weekly biases by station, based on the use of the nominal CoG correction of **174mm**

Reference Frame of Analysis: **SLRF2014**

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Count
Station A	4.8 ± 1.7	8	
Station B	1.0 ± 5.1	5	
Station C	-9.5 ± 7.1	7	
Station D	4.5 ± 3.5	9	
Station E	4.3 ± 2.0	3	
Station F	-6.5 ± 2.5	9	
Station G	-8.1 ± 3.0	8	
Station H	-9.7 ± 5.4	9	
Station I	-18.9 ± 3.3	9	
Station J	-5.5 ± 1.8	9	

OPEN JOINT-STOCK COMPANY - RESEARCH-AND-PRODUCTION CORPORATION "PRECISION SYSTEMS AND INSTRUMENTS"

Mass: 17 kg
Radius: 110 mm
2.5 times increased cross-section compared to BLITS (Sokolov et al., 2016).

Zero-signature target.
Made of radiation-resistant glass with high-reflectivity dielectric interference phase-shift coating instead of aluminum coating, used for BLITS.

BLITS-M2 (Ball Lens In The Space-M2)

Mass: 17 kg
Diameter: 210 mm

Small signature effect.
Made of glass to avoid induction of eddy currents, preventing the satellite spin slow down.

Geodetic Laser Autonomic Spherical Satellite (GLASS)

- Final version of ITRF2020 released by ITRS on April 15, 2022
- Developing the SLRF2020 edition, to include historical stations not part of ITRF2020
- A new ILRS ASC analysis product under development; required for proper use of ITRF2020:
 - ◆ The new approach in handling systematic errors relies on the SSEM model valid for 1993.0 - 2021.0
 - ◆ To use ITRF2020 beyond 2021.0 an extension of SSEM is necessary as well as continuous maintenance
 - ◆ A new weekly ILRS solution which will adjust freely station positions, orbits and station systematics is under development
 - ◆ This product will lag the standard weekly series by a week, in order to capture all tracking data
 - ◆ The results will be used to extend the SSEM by a week and into the future, and insert “breaks” in case a change in the mean bias of a station is identified with sufficient confidence
- Improved corrections in the current model for target signature corrections (CoG) are being calculated, including the consideration of new targets (LARES-2)
- Include LARES and LARES-2 satellites in the operational data products (2023)
- Estimation of low degree/order gravity field terms to be included in a future product (2023)
- Add loading corrections (at the observation level) to a special internal operational product (2023)

- Many geographic gaps, primarily in Latin America, Africa, and Oceania
- Mix of new and old technologies, levels of financial support, weather
- Lack of standardization in system hardware and operations
- Data quality issues (significant progress made in detecting and reducing systematics)
- Number of target satellites continues to increase as new missions use SLR for orbit determination and other applications ; currently tracking ~120 satellites, soon to be ~140 satellites

